

Airport Image and Quality of Services: The Impact of Crm on Promoting Customer Satisfaction

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Abstract:- This paper offers a framework for investigating the correlation between corporate image, service quality, customer relationship management (CRM), and customer satisfaction. Furthermore, it also aims to demonstrate the importance of CRM to improve an organization's image and the quality of services provided to achieve customer satisfaction. The conceptual framework was tested at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport in Jakarta, Indonesia with data collected from 235 customers using the service. The hypothesized relationships between variables were analyzed using a structural equation model. The results of this research show that there is a positive significant indirect (partially mediated) effect of corporate image and service quality on customer satisfaction through CRM. The model confirms that a credible corporate image, providing high-quality services, and maintaining good relationships with customers result in high customer satisfaction.

Keywords:- Component; Formatting; Style; Styling; Insert (Keywords Corporate Image, Service Quality, Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Customer Satisfaction).

I. INTRODUCTION

Airports face some problems when aiding passengers, including for example, the result of terminal congestion, irregular demand for airport service users, disclosure to local disturbances and external events, involvement of many staff and service providers, and fragmented passenger segments leading to varying hopes regarding quality service. Despite attempts to solidify some of the key activities at airports such as check-in, baggage drop-off, security screening, passport control, and departure gates, that is to say, unlike in manufacturing, where organizations attempt for 'flawless' creation, it is nearly unmanageable to dodge defects in service delivery. In contrast, service failures are unavoidable at airports, and temporary failures with some service attributes may have little impact on overall customer satisfaction. Other impacts may be significant and in turn, affect customer satisfaction such as the image of airport service management companies and how airport managers invest to maintain good relations with customers who use airport services.

Organizations should focus on service quality and customer relationship management, especially the focus dimensions on prioritizing customer satisfaction (Al-Gasawneh et al., 2022). Service quality and customer

satisfaction are connected as two important concepts in marketing theory and practice (Satti, Babar, & Ahmad, 2021). Meeting customer needs is a challenging process, particularly for companies with a large customer base. As customer service moves towards digitization, organizations, in this case, must improve employee skills related to the process of managing customer relationships in exchange for increasing customer satisfaction, maintaining loyalty, and increasing the number of new customers (Berg et al., 2022).

Another important thing that influences customer satisfaction is the company image. Customers expect better service quality from service organizations that have a good corporate image compared to other companies (Cabral, 2000). Corporate image not only ensures the desired service quality but also makes customers satisfied and loyal to service providers (Rahman, 2012). Although the research by Kurniati et al. (2015) states there is an insignificant connection between corporate image and customer satisfaction, this study attempts to fill the gap by adding the CRM variable as a mediator variable. In addition, this paper also contributes to adding to the literature related to customer satisfaction by focusing on corporate image, service quality, and CRM variables.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Corporate Image and Customer Satisfaction

Based on the experience of customer satisfaction and the transaction-driven nature of customer satisfaction many researchers have claimed that corporate image is a function of the accumulative influence of customer satisfaction/dissatisfaction (Oliver & Linda, 1981; Bolton & Drew, 1991; Fornell, 1992; Khoo, 2020; Keskar et al., 2020; Boujaddaine & Taqi, 2021) and corporate image are important aspects for evaluating customer satisfaction when services are difficult to assess (Andreassen & Lindestad, 1998; Özkan et al., 2019; Foroudi, 2020).

Corporate image shows an important role in how service-oriented organizations preserve customer loyalty (Harris & Goode, 2004; Khan, Yasir, & Khan, 2021; Simakhajornboon & Sirichodnisakorn, 2022). Satisfactory corporate image is measured as a key aspect of controlling customer satisfaction and behavioral intention (Faria & Mendes, 2013; Babu & Thomas, 2021). Based on the literature review above, hypothesis 1 is determined as follows.

➤ *H1: Corporate Image has A Positive and Significant Effect on Customer Satisfaction*

B. The Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to customer experience based on the particular quality of service received. Customer satisfaction is in line with customer loyalty which is determined by the quality of service provided by the organization to its customers (Al-Tit, 2015; 2020). Jahanshani et al. (2011) and Abror et al. (2019) added consumer satisfaction is significantly impacted by service quality. Other researchers empirically support this and confirm that service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction (Pakurár et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2019; Fida et al., 2020; Uzir et al., 2021).

Several researchers stated the importance of organizations always paying attention to service quality and customer satisfaction (González et al., 2007; Kuo et al., 2016). This is supported by the results of Saut and Song's research (2022); Rita et al. (2019); Talegani et al. (2011); Marinkovic et al. (2020); Al-Karim (2019); and Liao (2012) who stated that service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction and the attributes of service quality affect customer satisfaction (Ju et al., 2019). Based on the literature review above, hypothesis 2 is determined as follows.

➤ *H2: Service Quality has A Positive and Significant Effect on Customer Satisfaction*

C. Corporate Image, Service Quality, Customer Relation Management (CRM), and Customer Satisfaction

The paper conducted by Mainardes et al. (2021) showed the quality of airport services could affect trust, perceived value, customer satisfaction, and the spitting image of airport management companies. Spreading the existing literature, which is limited to investigating the services provided only by airlines, it is evident that the effect of the constructs analyzed does not only apply to services delivered by airlines, but also at airport terminals.

The results lead to the deduction that airport terminal managers and administrators must ensure the quality of services provided. Guaranteed quality of service can affect directly and indirectly the image of the airport management company. Furthermore, Karyose et al. (2017) in research on the financial sector confirm the relationship between service quality, corporate image, and Customer Relationship Marketing on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, where research findings state there is a positive and significant correlation between variables and customer satisfaction mediates the connection between service quality, image company, and Customer Relationship Marketing on customer loyalty.

➤ *Thus, based on the literature review above, hypotheses 3, 4, and 5 are determined as follows.*

- *H3: Corporate image has a positive and significant effect through CRM on customer satisfaction*
- *H4: Service quality has a positive and significant effect through CRM on customer satisfaction*
- *H5: CRM mediates positively and significantly the effect of corporate image and service quality on customer satisfaction.*

Fig 1 CRM customer satisfaction Daigram

III. RESEARCH METHOD

➤ *Data Analysis Technique*

The research data were analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis technique or structural equation model which integrates data analysis of measurement models, structural models, and Goodness of Fit (GoF) analysis simultaneously using software. Linear Structural Relationship (LISREL) 8.80 (Joreskog & Sorbom, 2008).

➤ *Data Collection Techniques*

The primary data collection technique used by the researchers in this paper was by giving questionnaires to a sample of 235 research customers using Soekarno Hatta airport services, Jakarta with a convenience sampling technique.

➤ *Measurement Scale*

Items for each variable are measured using an interval scale, namely the Likert scale (Strongly Agree = 5, Agree = 4, Neutral = 3, Disagree = 2, Strongly Disagree = 1). The customer satisfaction variable refers to research conducted by Mainardes et al. (2021) with the addition of 4 items from Prentice and Kadan (2019) with 2 (two) constructs, namely performance and the right choice.

The Customer Relationship Management (CRM) variable refers to a paper written by Nyadzayo and Khajehzadeh (2016) which includes constructs of trust and commitment. Furthermore, the service quality variable refers to research conducted by Prentice and Wang (2019) with the constructs of facilities, check-in, servicescape, security, and ambiance. Items from the corporate image variable refer to Chien and Chi (2019) with the constructs of enterprise, informality, and competence.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. *Descriptive Analysis of Research Variables*

The following describes the analysis of the description of the research variables.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Statistics					
		CRM	SQ	CI	CS
N	Valid	235	235	235	235
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.9574	3.4603	3.1927	3.0695
Median		3.3333	3.5882	3.4286	3.3333
Mode		3.56	3.76	3.43	3.67
Std. Deviation		1.00125	0.54038	1.02078	1.17393
Variance		1.003	0.292	1.042	1.378
Minimum		1	2.29	1	1
Maximum		4.89	4.94	5	5

Source: Results of SPSS Data Processing

Based on Table 1 above, it can be seen that the average score for the research variable is 3.1699 on a scale of 1 to 5. This illustrates that the majority of respondents stated that the research variable was in the appropriate range, namely a score of 2.9574 for the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) variable. A score of 3.4603 for the service quality variable, a score of 3.1927 for the corporate image variable, and a score of 3.0695 for the customer satisfaction variable. Thus, the research variables are in the appropriate category.

B. *Validity and Reliability Test Analysis*

Table 2 Construct Validity and Reliability Test Results

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor (L)	Validity	AVE	CR	Information
Corporate Image	CI1	0.85	Valid	0.729	0.997	reliable
	CI2	0.94	Valid			
	CI3	0.95	Valid			
	CI4	0.95	Valid			
	CI5	0.95	Valid			
	CI6	0.85	Valid			
	CI7	0.87	Valid			
Service Quality	SQ1	0.87	Valid	0.696	0.993	reliable
	SQ2	0.91	Valid			
	SQ3	0.89	Valid			
	SQ4	0.92	Valid			
	SQ5	0.88	Valid			
	SQ6	0.88	Valid			
	SQ7	0.89	Valid			
	SQ8	0.88	Valid			
	SQ9	0.88	Valid			
	SQ10	0.87	Valid			
	SQ11	0.84	Valid			
CRM	CRM1	0.92	Valid	0.718	0.985	reliable
	CRM2	0.91	Valid			
	CRM3	0.92	Valid			
	CRM4	0.9	Valid			
	CRM5	0.89	Valid			
	CRM6	0.88	Valid			
	CRM7	0.89	Valid			
	CRM8	0.89	Valid			
	CRM9	0.89	Valid			
Customer Satisfaction	CS1	0.94	Valid	0.77	0.964	reliable
	CS2	0.95	Valid			
	CS3	0.94	Valid			
	CS4	0.94	Valid			
	CS5	0.93	Valid			
	CS6	0.89	Valid			

Source: Processed Data (LISREL 8.8)

Based on the results of the construct validity and reliability tests (Table 2), the corporate image variable structural model test will be measured by 7 indicators declared valid and service quality measured by 11 indicators declared valid. Furthermore, the CRM variable is measured by 9 indicators which are declared valid and the customer satisfaction variable is measured by 6 indicators which are declared valid.

C. Direct & Indirect Effect Analysis

Chi-Square=862.78, df=489, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.057

Fig 2 Estimation Results of the SEM (Standardized Solution) Model

Chi-Square=862.78, df=489, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.057

Fig 3 Estimation Results of the SEM Model (t-value)

Table 3 Direct Effect

Path	Std. Path Coeff	t hitung	P value
CI → CRM	0.3	5.96	< 0.01
SQ → CRM	0.66	11.27	< 0.01
CI → CS	0.3	6.26	< 0.01
SQ → CS	0.2	3.23	< 0.01
CRM → CS	0.49	6.95	< 0.01

Source: Processed Data (2023)

Table 4 Indirect Effect Test Analysis (Indirect Effect)

a	b	sa	sb	t	p-value 1 tail	p-value 2 tail
0.30	0.49	0.05	0.07	4.556	< 0.01	< 0.01
0.66	0.49	0.059	0.07	5,934	< 0.01	< 0.01

Source: Sobel Test Results

Table 5 Hypothesis Testing Results

No	Question	Coefficient	t	P	Information
H1	Corporate image has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction	0.3	6,26	<0.01	accepted
H2	Service quality has a significant positive effect on customer relationship management (CRM)	0.66	11.27	< 0.01	accepted
H3	Corporate image has a positive and significant indirect effect on customer satisfaction through CRM	0.15	4.556	<0.01	accepted
H4	Service quality has a positive and significant indirect effect on customer satisfaction through CRM	0.32	5.934	<0.01	accepted
H5	Corporate image and service quality have a positive and significant indirect effect on customer quality through CRM	Koefisien jalur CI = 0,15; Koefisien jalur SQ = 0,32	t CI = 4,556; t SQ = 5,934	P value CI < 0.01; P value SQ < 0,001	accepted

- The study results state that corporate image positively and significantly affects customer satisfaction. This supports the results of research conducted by Faria and Mendes (2013); Babu and Thomas (2021) who think that a good corporate image is a key factor influencing customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions. It also fills a research gap from Kurniati et al. (2015) who concluded that there is a positive but not significant relationship between corporate image and customer satisfaction.
- The paper results state that service quality positively and significantly affects customer satisfaction. This supports the research of Hapsari, et al. (2017) which states that there is a positive relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction which will ultimately result in the maximum profit generated by the organization. Service quality comes from the satisfaction of the company's employees, which has a direct impact on service quality, and will affect customer satisfaction. Therefore, it is important for organizations to always pay attention to service quality and customer satisfaction (González et al., 2007; Kuo et al., 2009).
- The results of the study state that corporate image has a positive and significant indirect effect on customer satisfaction through Customer Relationship Management (CRM). For this reason, it can be stated that Customer Relationship Management (CRM) mediates (partially mediation) the relationship between corporate image and customer satisfaction. This empirically supports that customer relationship management (CRM) can form a positive corporate image in the minds of customers. The company's strategy in establishing relationships with customers will be able to form a level of customer loyalty that is satisfied with the company's performance. It was concluded that marketing strategies carried out by establishing relationships with customers will affect customer satisfaction (Mithas, Krishnan, & Fornell, 2005; Hayati et al., 2020).

➤ *Implications*

This study provides a significant theoretical contribution from a broader theoretical perspective and adds to the current airport-related literature to explore and understand the importance of customer relationship management (Customer Relationship Management) as an internal attribute related to research objectives. This research is also initial research related to the study of airports which places the Customer Relationship Management variable as mediating the relationship between corporate image and service quality on customer satisfaction. The findings from this research can help airport authorities/managers to better identify the necessary improvements and develop appropriate strategies. Airports should take initiatives to improve customer satisfaction by continuously monitoring and assessing service standards and maintaining a good corporate image.

V. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

➤ *Some of the Research Limitations are as follows;*

- The number of variables used to predict customer satisfaction from Soekarno-Hatta airport service users, in Jakarta is limited to corporate image, service quality, and Customer Relationship Management (CRM). It is known that many factors can affect customer satisfaction such as customer perceived value, customer loyalty, and so on.
- The limited number of respondents studied was due to the limited time of the researchers and the busyness of the respondents which limited the researchers from being able to increase the number of research subjects. The more respondents involved, the higher the level of research accuracy.
- The limited research sites involved only one research object, namely Soekarno-Hatta Airport, Jakarta with PT Angkasa Pura 2 (Persero), Tbk as the only management and service provider company which is a State-Owned Enterprise in the field of air transportation industry and provide optimal services related to aviation facilities.
- The limited availability of time for researchers in the process of completing research so that the research method is determined to only use quantitative method designs.

VI. SUGGESTION

Theoretically, this research supports the factors that influence customer satisfaction. This research can be developed and expanded towards a more in-depth and integrated understanding, of both internal and external factors that make a major contribution in determining attitudes and behavior that have an impact on increasing customer satisfaction. Theoretical suggestions for further research are expected to look for other variables that may have a relationship and influence on customer satisfaction variables; it is necessary to increase the number of research respondents so that the research results can be generalized and the research object/research location needs to be expanded to airports managed by other airport management companies.

Future research should have sufficient time to collect research data, so that a larger number of respondents and research subjects can be obtained, and it is possible to conduct a mixed research method (mixed method). The results of this research can theoretically broaden research insights related to marketing management studies, for example for further research related to the understanding and application of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) variables.

From the results of research, discussion, and conclusions, researchers provide applicable suggestions for airport management, PT Angkasa Pura 2 (Persero), Tbk to focus more on managing Customer Relationship Management (CRM) as the basis for companies/organizations in creating a good work

environment for their employees to be able to work even better to fulfill customer satisfaction; improve the company's image, both domestically and internationally based on Indonesian cultural values, and always make innovations related to service provision and improve the quality of services provided.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Al-Gasawneh, J. A., AlZubi, K. N., Anuar, M. M., Padlee, S. F., ul-Haque, A., & Saputra, J. (2022). Marketing Performance Sustainability in the Jordanian Hospitality Industry: The Roles of Customer Relationship Management and Service Quality. *Sustainability*, 14(2), 803.
- [2]. Satti, Z. W., Babar, S. F., & Ahmad, H. M. (2021). Exploring the mediating role of service quality in the association between sensory marketing and customer satisfaction. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 32(7-8), 719-736.
- [3]. Berg, J., Buesing, E., Hurst, P., Lai, V., & Mukhopadhyay, S. (2022). The state of customer care in 2022. McKinsey & Company.
- [4]. Cabral, L. (2000). Stretching Firm and Brand Reputation. *The Rand Journal of Economics*. Mount Morris, 31(4), 658-674. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2307/2696353>.
- [5]. R. Nicole, "Title of paper with the only first word capitalized," *J. Name Stand. Abbrev.*, in press.
- [6]. Rahman, M. S. (2012). Service quality, corporate image, and customer's satisfaction towards customers perception: an exploratory study on telecom customers in Bangladesh. *Business Intelligence Journal*, 5(1).
- [7]. Kurniati, R. R., Suharyono, Hamid, D., & Arifin, Z. (2015). The effect of customer relationship marketing (CRM) and service quality on corporate image, value, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.7, No.11.
- [8]. Oliver, R. L., & Linda, G. (1981). Effect of satisfaction and its antecedents on consumer preference and intention. *ACR North American Advances*.
- [9]. Bolton, R. N., & Drew, J. H. (1991). A longitudinal analysis of the impact of service changes on customer attitudes. *The Journal of Marketing*, 1-9.
- [10]. Fornell, C. (1992). A national customer satisfaction barometer: The Swedish experience. *Journal of Marketing*, 56(1), 6-21.
- [11]. Khoo, K. L. (2020). A study of service quality, corporate image, customer satisfaction, revisit intention and word-of-mouth: evidence from the KTV industry. *PSU Research Review*.
- [12]. Keskar, M. Y., Pandey, N., & Patwardhan, A. A. (2020). Development of a conceptual framework for Internet banking customer satisfaction index. *International Journal of Electronic Banking*, 2(1), 55-76.
- [13]. Boujaddaine, S. & Taqi, A. (2021). Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction and Recommendation of Mobile Banking Services in Morocco. *European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 6(3).
- [14]. Andreassen, T. W., & Lindestad, B. (1998). The effect of corporate image in the formation of customer loyalty. *Journal of Service Research*, 1(1), 82-92.
- [15]. Özkan, P., Süer, S., Keser, İ. K., & Kocakoç, İ. D. (2019). The effect of service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty: The mediation of perceived value of services, corporate image, and corporate reputation. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*.
- [16]. Foroudi, P. (2020). Corporate brand strategy: drivers and outcomes of hotel industry's brand orientation. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 88, 102519.
- [17]. Harris, L. C., & Goode, M. M. (2004). The four levels of loyalty and the pivotal role of trust: a study of online service dynamics. *Journal of Retailing*, 80(2), 139-158.
- [18]. Khan, M. A., Yasir, M., & Khan, M. A. (2021). Factors Affecting Customer Loyalty in the Services Sector: Reference: Khan, MA, Yasir, M. & Khan, MA (2021). Factors Affecting Customer Loyalty in the Services Sector. *Journal of Tourism and Services*, 22 (12), 184-197. *Journal of Tourism and Services*, 12(22), 184-197.
- [19]. Simakhajornboon, P., & Sirichodnisakorn, C. (2022). The effect of customer perception of CSR initiative on customer loyalty in the hotel industry. *Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences Studies (Former Name Silpakorn University Journal of Social Sciences, Humanities, And Arts)*, 384-396.
- [20]. Faria, N., & Mendes, L. (2013). Organizational image's partial mediation role between quality and users' satisfaction. *The Service Industries Journal*, 33(13-14), 1275-1293.
- [21]. Babu, F. & Thomas, S. (2021). Quality management practices as a driver of employee satisfaction: exploring the mediating role of organizational image. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*.
- [22]. Al-Tit, A. (2020). E-commerce drivers and barriers and their impact on e-customer loyalty in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). *Verslas: Teorija ir Praktika/Business: Theory and Practice*, 21(1), 146-157.
- [23]. Jahanshani, A. A., Hajizadeh, G. M. A., Mirdhamadi, S. A., Nawaser, K., & Khaksar, S. M. S. (2011). Study the effects of customer service and product quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(7), 253-260.
- [24]. Abror, A., Patrisia, D., Engriani, Y., Evanita, S., Yasri, Y., & Dastgir, S. (2019). Service quality, religiosity, customer satisfaction, customer engagement, and Islamic bank's customer loyalty. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*.

- [25]. Pakurár, M., Haddad, H., Nagy, J., Popp, J., & Oláh, J. (2019). The service quality dimensions that affect customer satisfaction in the Jordanian banking sector. *Sustainability*, 11(4), 1113.
- [26]. Huang, P. L., Lee, B. C., & Chen, C. C. (2019). The influence of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the B2B technology service industry. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 30(13-14), 1449-1465.
- [27]. Fida, B. A., Ahmed, U., Al-Balushi, Y., & Singh, D. (2020). Impact of service quality on customer loyalty and customer satisfaction in Islamic Banks in the Sultanate of Oman. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 2158244020919517.
- [28]. Uzir, M. U. H., Al Halbusi, H., Thurasamy, R., Hock, R. L. T., Aljaberi, M. A., Hasan, N., & Hamid, M. (2021). The effects of service quality, perceived value and trust in-home delivery service personnel on customer satisfaction: Evidence from a developing country. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 63, 102721.
- [29]. González, M. E. A., Comesaña, L. R., & Brea, J. A. F. (2007). Assessing tourist behavioral intentions through perceived service quality and customer satisfaction. *Journal of business research*, 60(2), 153-160.
- [30]. Kuo, T., Tsai, G. Y., Lu, I. Y., & Chang, J. S. (2016). Relationships among service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty: A case study on mobile shopping APPs. In *Proceedings of the 17th Asia Pacific Industrial Engineering and Management System Conference*, Taipei, Taiwan (pp. 7-10).
- [31]. Saut, M & Song, V. (2022). Influences of airport service quality, satisfaction, and image on behavioral intention towards destination visit. *Urban, Planning and Transport Research*, 10:1, 82-109, DOI: 10.1080/21650020.2022.2054857. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21650020.2022.2054857>.
- [32]. Saut, M & Song, V. (2022). Influences of airport service quality, satisfaction, and image on behavioral intention towards destination visit. *Urban, Planning and Transport Research*, 10:1, 82-109, DOI: 10.1080/21650020.2022.2054857. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21650020.2022.2054857>.
- [33]. Rita, P., Oliveira, T., & Farisa, A. (2019). The impact of e-service quality and customer satisfaction on customer behavior in online shopping. *Heliyon*, 5(10), e02690.
- [34]. Taleghani, M., Biabani, S., Gilaninia, S., Rahbarinia, S. A., & Mousavian, S. J. (2011). The relationship between customer satisfaction and relationship marketing benefits. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 1(3).
- [35]. Marinković, V., Đorđević, A., & Kalinić, Z. (2020). The moderating effects of gender on customer satisfaction and continuance intention in mobile commerce: a UTAUT-based perspective. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 32(3), 306-318.
- [36]. Al Karim, R. (2019). Influence of service quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in the private banking sector of Bangladesh: A PLS approach. *Journal of Marketing and Information Systems*, 2(2), 8-17.
- [37]. Liao, K. H. (2012). The casual effects of service quality, brand image, and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty in the leisure resort enterprise. *China-USA Business Review*, 11(5).
- [38]. Ju, Y., Back, K. J., Choi, Y., & Lee, J. S. (2019). Exploring Airbnb service quality attributes and their asymmetric effects on customer satisfaction. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 77, 342-352.
- [39]. Karyose, H., Astuti, W., & Ferdiansjah, A. (2017). Customer loyalty: the effect of service quality, corporate image, customer relationship marketing, and customer satisfaction as intervening variable-an empirical analysis of bank customers in Malang city. *Marketing and Branding Research* 4(2017) 336-347.
- [40]. Joreskog, K. G. & Sorbom, D. (2008). LISREL 8.80 User's Guide (with software). Scientific Software International. IL: Lincolnwood.
- [41]. Nyadzayo, M.W. & Khajehzadeh, S. (2016). The antecedents of customer loyalty: A moderated mediation model of customer relationship management quality and brand image. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2016.02.002>.
- [42]. Prentice, C., & Kadan, M. (2019). The role of airport service quality in airport and destination choice. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 47, 40-48.
- [43]. Prentice, C., Dominique Lopes, S., & Wang, X. (2020). The impact of artificial intelligence and employee service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 29(7), 739-756.
- [44]. Chien, L. & Chi, S. Y. (2019). Corporate image as a mediator between service quality and customer satisfaction: difference across categorized exhibitors. *Heliyon* 5 (2019) e01307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01307>.
- [45]. Kurniati, R. R., Suharyono, Hamid, D., & Arifin, Z. (2015). The effect of customer relationship marketing (CRM) and service quality on corporate image, value, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.7, No.11.
- [46]. Hapsari, R., Clemes, M. D., & Dean, D. (2017). The impact of service quality, customer engagement, and selected marketing constructs on airline passenger loyalty. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*.
- [47]. González, M. E. A., Comesaña, L. R., & Brea, J. A. F. (2007). Assessing tourist behavioral intentions through perceived service quality and customer satisfaction. *Journal of business research*, 60(2), 153-160.

- [48]. Kuo, T., Tsai, G. Y., Lu, I. Y., & Chang, J. S. (2016). Relationships among service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty: A case study on mobile shopping APPs. In Proceedings of the 17th Asia Pacific Industrial Engineering and Management System Conference, Taipei, Taiwan (pp. 7-10).
- [49]. Mithas, S., Krishnan, M. S., & Fornell, C. (2005). Why do customer relationship management applications affect customer satisfaction? *Journal of Marketing*, 69(4), 201-209.
- [50]. Hayati, S., Suroso, A., Suliyanto, S., & Kaukab, M. (2020). Customer satisfaction is a mediation between micro banking image, customer relationship, and customer loyalty. *Management Science Letters*, 10(11), 2561-2570.